

INNOVATIONS IN THE BANKING SECTOR

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Introduction

The current stage of development of the global banking system is taking place in conditions of increased competition and crisis phenomena in financial markets. One of the main factors of successful development of banking activity is the policy of constant innovation. Currently, innovations are key factors of stability, competitiveness and sustainable economic growth of banks. Banking innovations as a catalyst for banking activity The current realities of the banking business allow us to clearly identify three main catalysts for banking innovation: - the globalization of global financial markets and banking services markets– - increasing competition from the banking and non-banking sectors– - the global financial crisis. The concept of "Banking innovation" has its own characteristics. According to Prof. I. T. Balabanova, "Banking innovation is the final result of the bank's innovation activity implemented in the form of a new banking product or operation," and innovation activity is understood to be "the systematic process of creating and implementing

innovations." Approximately the same point of view is shared in their works by other researchers: E. A. Zolotova, A.V. Kaltyrin, V. S. Vikulov, P. V. Semikova. According to O. I. Lavrushina, "Banking innovation, or a set of new banking products and services— is a synthetic concept about the bank's activities aimed at generating additional income in the process of creating favorable conditions for the formation and placement of resource potential through the introduction of innovations that assist customers in making a profit." So, banking innovation is the final result of the scientific and technical activities of the bank, embodied in the form of a new or improved product or service, aimed at better meeting the existing needs of customers or the formation of new ones in the process of managing the resource potential of the bank. What motivates banks, what makes them move away from traditional methods of doing business? What or who? The answer is simple — a new reality and human needs. What has changed for you and me in this century! Speed! We are rapidly rushing forward and do not want services that provide a high quality of our life to slow down. They should not just keep up with us, they should be ahead of us! As long as we are in commodity-money relations, we will always need banks. But now we are making new demands on them and remain only where the range of services is wide enough to meet our needs. What does a modern customer expect from a bank? Bain Experts & Company [1] summarized the needs and expectations of consumers in relation to banks and identified the following needs. The search for information about the bank's products and services should be simple and accessible. The assistance of the bank's employees would be available at any time - by phone, Internet or directly at the branch. So that when registering a product or service, you can switch between channels: for example, by starting to make a payment on a mobile device, complete a transaction from a computer. So that the cost of products/services is the same in all channels. So that bank accounts can be accessed

from different devices. So that most of the daily banking operations can be carried out through digital channels. So that purchases, payments and money transfers can be carried out using a smartphone. So that operations are safe, fast and cheap. So that feedback from the bank is simple and accessible, and the reaction to it is prompt (including in social networks). Consequently, banks have no other way but innovative.

Digital in a bank — what is it? Consider a number of innovations in the banking sector. The largest Russian banks are betting on the development of remote services, transferring business to the digital sphere. The user essence of digitalization is - speed, - transparency of processes and - ease of interaction. This is comfortable for customers, useful and profitable for banks, whose administrative and economic expenses are reduced [2] and terminals will go to the periphery, branches will deal with complex products or become a place for holding various events with customers, performing routine operations less and less. It is the digital environment that will allow expanding the range of services provided by the bank to customers. Now the main thing is to find the right way to solve specific problems, develop your own or apply a technological technique created and successfully tested by others. The main thing we understand is that business and IT[3] need to be connected.

NFC (Near Field Communication) technology turns a mobile phone into a virtual bank card. In addition, it is fashionable in the digital sphere to develop messengers as a new service channel, but in fact banks are engaged in improving their basic product in digital, as we saw with the example of BCS bank. Which is not bad at all, because most Internet and mobile banks are not perfect yet. Not all operations are available to people in remote channels, not all of the available ones are implemented conveniently and clearly. Although there are exceptions. However, even the most advanced ones have call centers where real people work, since there

are not enough fully automated bots that give answers to certain questions. And someone has to answer the client if the question is not closed by the bot. Answer quickly and bring the question to the desired solution.

Startups [6] are actively turning this into a mainstream service, but this approach is still a novelty for banks. That is, the messenger is a convenient channel for banks to interact with customers. In digital, there is a channel that allows customers to communicate with each other and the bank. Chats are an online communication channel of the bank with customers, ideally - instant messaging, question - answer. That is, chats are essentially a call center, and part of the work can be shifted to bots, special programs that perform any actions automatically and/or according to a given schedule through the same interfaces as a regular user. The second way of chat development is a service for conducting operations. The market has already developed technologies where you can transfer money to each other directly in the chat, while chatting not only with the bank, but also with friends. Many banks welcome more informal chat than through call centers, the culture of the online environment is appropriate here: emoticons, abbreviations, "greetings", "smacks".

Big Data in the bank, Bank marketers work with a huge amount of information, segmenting customers into groups, for which the product is then developed. Big Data or big data is a technology that allows you to quickly process large amounts of information. Big data is determined not only by an unimaginable volume — and the amount in the databases goes to millions of gigabytes — but also by a special, chaotic structure, before which traditional mathematics gives in. For example, HSBC Bank [7] has implemented big data technologies as part of a solution to counter credit card fraud. As a result, the efficiency of the fraud detection service has tripled, and the accuracy of its detection has increased tenfold. During the first

two weeks of operation, seven HSBC security specialists identified new criminal groups and schemes with a total potential damage of more than \$ 10 million.

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